

Chronic Venous Insufficiency in Obese Individuals: Focus on the Priority of Bariatric vs. Venous Surgery: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

Background: Chronic Venous Insufficiency (CVI) is a progressive disorder characterized by venous valve dysfunction, venous hypertension, and impaired venous return. Obesity exacerbates CVI progression through mechanical compression, systemic inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, and lymphatic impairment. Given the rising global prevalence of obesity, CVI is increasingly prevalent and challenging to manage. This systematic review aims to: (1) assess obesity's impact on CVI pathophysiology and progression, (2) evaluate diagnostic and treatment challenges in obese individuals, and (3) analyze the clinical prioritization between bariatric surgery and venous surgery in obese patients with CVI.

Methods: A systematic search of PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar was conducted for studies published between 2000 and 2025. Eligible publications included randomized controlled trials (RCTs), observational studies, meta-analyses, and cohort studies. Search terms included: obesity, body mass index (BMI), chronic venous insufficiency, venous ulcer, varicose vein, deep vein thrombosis (DVT), bariatric surgery, endovenous laser ablation (EVLA), iliac vein stenting (IVS), mechanochemical ablation (MOCA), and sclerotherapy.

Results: Obesity contributes to CVI through increased intra-abdominal pressure, venous reflux, inflammatory mediators, and calf muscle dysfunction. Evidence supports bariatric surgery as a first-line strategy in morbidly obese individuals, improving venous hypertension, and long-term vascular outcomes.

Venous interventions including endovenous thermal ablation (ETA) and sclerotherapy, demonstrate improved effective post weight loss due to lower perioperative risks and better outcomes.

Conclusion: In morbidly obese patients with CVI, bariatric surgery may be prioritized to address underlying venous hypertension. However, in acute complications (e.g., active ulcers, thrombosis), venous interventions may be prioritized. An integrated, multidisciplinary approach optimizing both weight reduction and vascular treatment improves long-term outcomes.

Introduction

Chronic venous diseases (CVDs) comprise a spectrum of conditions affecting the venous system, including varicose veins, chronic venous insufficiency (CVI), deep vein thrombosis (DVT), and venous ulcers. These conditions arise from venous hypertension primarily caused by valve incompetence, obstruction, or calf muscle pump dysfunction. The pathogenesis involves a cascade of events, starting the venous hypertension that leads to endothelial dysfunction, inflammation, and leukocyte activation. This triggers the release of inflammatory mediators, cytokines, and proteases, which degrade the extracellular matrix and weaken the venous wall. Over time, these pathological changes result in venous dilation, reflux, and chronic inflammation, contributing to the clinical manifestations of CVD, such as edema, skin pigmentation, and ulceration (1, 2).

Obesity, particularly abdominal obesity, imposes mechanical and biochemical stress on the venous system. Studies indicate that individuals with a higher body mass index (BMI) are at an elevated risk of developing CVD (3). Increased BMI is associated with more severe venous disease symptoms, a higher likelihood of deep venous reflux, and emphasizing the importance of weight management in mitigating these conditions (4). In patients with CVD, a higher BMI correlates with increased clinical severity, and more severe skin manifestations (5). Elevated BMI is associated with the enlargement of great saphenous veins, and greater progression to advanced CVI stages (6). Furthermore, increased body weight independently contributes to a heightened risk of developing varicose veins (7, 8). A high BMI has also been identified as a risk factor for developing deep vein thrombosis (DVT) following knee arthroscopic procedures (9). Additionally, a higher visceral adiposity index (VAI) is associated with increased inflammation and endothelial dysfunction which contributes to progression of CVI severity (10).

Waist circumference (WC), a marker of abdominal obesity, more strongly predicts venous thromboembolism (VTE) risk than BMI due to direct intra-abdominal pressure effects.

Individuals with elevated WC were found to have a 53% greater risk of developing VTE compared to those with normal WC values (11). Similarly, Cheng Du. reported that obesity-related factors including BMI, basal metabolic rate, hip circumference, and WC indicate a strong positive correlation with the occurrence of VTE and varicose veins. Among these factors, WC independently mediates these conditions, irrespective of the other three factors (12).

Genetic studies further support this evidence, as demonstrated by Shan et al., who found that genetically predicted obesity significantly increases DVT risk, with each standard deviation rise in BMI corresponding to elevated odds of thrombosis (13). Given the rising burden of obesity worldwide, understanding its mechanistic role in CVD pathogenesis is crucial for risk stratification and therapeutic interventions. This review systematically explores: (1) the pathophysiology of CVI in obesity, (2) outcomes of venous surgeries in obese individuals, and (3) the role and prioritization of bariatric surgery in treatment sequencing.

Pathophysiology of chronic venous diseases in obese individuals

Obesity leads to increased intra-abdominal pressure, which hinders venous return from the lower extremities, inducing venous hypertension. Persistent venous hypertension may induce valvular dysfunction, venous reflux, and chronic inflammation, ultimately resulting in clinical symptoms including leg swelling, pain, and skin changes. Additionally, the excess weight places a direct strain on the venous walls, exacerbating the risk of venous dilation and varicosities (14, 15).

Biochemically, obesity is associated with a pro-inflammatory state characterized by elevated levels of cytokines and adipocytes, such as TNF- α and IL-6. These inflammatory mediators contribute to endothelial dysfunction and impair the integrity of the venous walls. Furthermore, obesity is linked to hypercoagulability, which increases the risk of thrombotic complications in patients with CVD.

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This interplay between inflammation, coagulation, and venous hypertension underscores the multifactorial impact of obesity on CVD (16). Additionally, elevated fibronectin levels were observed in obesity, contributing to thrombo-inflammation. Fibronectin interacts with toll-like-receptor 4 (TLR-4), enhancing neutrophil extracellular traps (NET) formation and promoting thrombosis. Thus, fibronectin could be a potential therapeutic target to mitigate DVT risk in obesity (17).

Furthermore, in obesity, an accumulation of adipose tissue raises intra-abdominal pressure, leading to venous hypertension and disrupting normal oscillatory flow. Moreover, the structural changes in veins due to obesity, including stiffening of venous walls, reduce their ability to accommodate physiologic oscillatory flow. Disrupted flow patterns increase clot formation risk, further exacerbating venous insufficiency (18).

Studies have demonstrated a significant association between abdominal volume index and elevated low-density lipoprotein levels, increased blood pressure, and reduced high-density lipoprotein levels (19).

In obese individuals, the diameter of the femoral vein was found to be significantly greater than that observed in their non-obese counterparts. Venous flow Parameters, including peak and minimum velocities, were notably lower among obese participants. Additionally, this group exhibited reduced shear stress and diminished venous amplitude. Furthermore, an inverse relationship was observed between waist-to-hip ratios and venous flow parameters. The venous flow characteristics in the lower limbs exhibit notable differences between obese and non-obese healthy individuals. These observations highlight the potential mechanical influence of abdominal adipose tissue, which may contribute to an increased likelihood of developing VTE and CVI (20). The observed differences in venous flow parameters, such as reduced velocities, shear stress, and venous amplitude in obese individuals, suggest that obesity may predispose individuals to venous disorders like VTE and CVI.

A current study indicated that elevation of the abdominal panniculus led to an increase in the diameter of the common femoral veins (CFV) and the left great saphenous vein, as well as a rise in venous flow volume in the left CFV. Moreover, the grade of obesity was correlated with the extent of venous disease (18). In a study by Wallenberg et al. involving patients with abdominal obesity, the application of cuff pressure did not significantly alter the diameter of lower limb veins or peak and mean blood flow velocity compared to conditions without cuff pressure. These findings suggest that abdominal obesity may contribute to venous stasis

and impaired venous return from the lower limbs, potentially increasing the risk of venous insufficiency (21).

Venous surgery in obese patients

Types of venous surgical interventions:

The primary interventions approaches include endogenous thermal ablation (ETA), iliac vein stenting (IVS), mechanochemical ablation (MOCA), cyanoacrylate embolization (CAE) and sclerotherapy. ETA which includes endogenous laser ablation (EVLA) and radiofrequency ablation (RFA) is widely used due to its high success rate in closing incompetent veins (22). IVS is particularly effective for deep vein obstructions, improving venous outflow and reducing symptoms (23). MOCA and CAE are minimally invasive techniques that offer faster recovery times and lower complication rates compared to traditional surgical methods (24, 25). Sclerotherapy is another approach in venous interventions, particularly for varicose veins. It is commonly used in combination with ETA to manage large varicosities (26). Moreover, its efficacy in treating venous ulcers is currently under evaluation, with promising preliminary results (27).

Efficacy and outcomes of venous surgeries in obese patients

Venous surgical interventions in obese patients present unique challenges due to altered vascular anatomy, increased intra-abdominal pressure, and systemic inflammation. Studies indicate that obese patients experience higher rates of venous reflux recurrence and lower satisfaction scores post-surgery. The increased adipose tissue complicates surgical access and reduces the efficacy of compression therapy, which is crucial for post-operative recovery (28). Studies suggest that while the infection rate in obese patients undergoing venous surgery is slightly higher than in those with a BMI below 30, the overall complication rates remain low with proper intraoperative management (29).

ETA remains the gold standard for treating CVI in obese patients, with an anatomical success rate exceeding 96% and long-term clinical benefits (30). Interestingly, obese patients with Clinical-Etiology-Anatomy-Pathophysiology classification (CEAP) C2 and C3 exhibited a comparable reduction in the venous clinical severity score (VCSS) and experienced substantial symptom relief, as measured by the HASTI (clinical symptom severity) score, relative to non-obese individuals following ETV (31). However, it has been observed that obese patients tend to experience extended post-procedural pain and an increased risk of infection (32). IVS has shown superior results in managing deep vein obstruction, with a primary potency rate of 92% and

significant relief (30). Recent studies suggest that IVS remains a viable treatment option for venous insufficiencies in obese patients, with outcomes comparable to those in non-obese individuals. In the study by Jayaraj et al. there is no significant differences in stent patency between obese and non-obese patients, suggesting that BMI alone may not be a strong predictor of midterm stenting success (33). Furthermore, in obese patients, iliac-caval stenting was found to be safe, with no mortality within 30 days, low morbidity (a 3% deep vein thrombosis rate), and 86% cumulative patency rate over 5 years. Thus, despite concerns about stent compression due to body habitus, ileocecal stenting remains a viable and effective treatment option (34). Recanalization may occur following venous surgical interventions, with obesity recognized as a contributing factor. The likelihood of recanalization varies across different venous interventions. It has been reported that high BMI does not affect the recanalization rate following ETA (32). Recent investigations into MOCA for CVD have shown a higher recanalization rate compared to RFA and

EVLA (35). Research has shown that patients with BMI>30kg/m² exhibit higher rates of recanalization compared to non-obese individuals. Moreover, vein diameters >10mm (not BMI alone) is the strongest recanalization predictor after MOCA. Accordingly, while MOCA achieves high initial closure rates obese patients may require additional interventions to maintain long-term vein occlusion. In general, despite the effectiveness of these interventions, obese patients often require longer recovery periods and higher post-operative care, including intensive compression therapy and lifestyle modifications (36). Moreover, although the risk of complications such as DVT and delayed wound healing is higher in the obese population (37), these complications appear to be more pronounced in individuals with a high BMI (38). Another important consideration is that BMI does not adequately reflect localized obesity. Accordingly, evaluating alternative weight parameters, such as WC, leg circumference, and waist-to-hip ratio, and their association with venous disease is of significant value (39).

Table 1. Impact of obesity on outcomes of chronic venous disease intervention surgeries

Study-Year	Type of CVD	Type of surgical intervention	Obesity Measure	Outcome
Ahmed et al. 2022 (40)	SVR	ETA	BMI>30	Increase recanalization risk on PVs
Bossart et al. 2023 (32)	IGSV	ETA	BMI>30	Increase pp pain and infection
Deol et al. 2020 (36)	Superficial system reflux>0.5, IGSV	ETA, phlebectomy, USGFS	BMI≥35	Increase number of thermal ablation, increase CIVIQ score
Rodriguez et al. 2019 (41)	IGSV, ISSV	RFA	*BMI>30 & BMI>40	Increase truncal recanalization
Casana et al. 2018 (42)	IGSV	RFA	BMI>25	Increase QoI score
Pisharody et al. 2024 (39)	IGSV, ISV	MOCA	BMI≥30	Increase rate of recanalization
Theivacumar et al. 2008 (43)	GSV reflux	EVLA	BMI≅25	No significant effect
Alongi et al. 2024 (44)	IGSV, VV	AMPS	BMI≥30	Increase recanalization rate
Turkmen et al. 2024(45)	IPV, VLU		BMI=29	No significant effect on N-OPV
Hager et al. 2016 (46)	VLU	EVLA,RFA, UGFS	BMI>50	Decrease PV closure rate
Shao et al. 2023 (47)	VLU	UGFS	BMI≅ 36	Treatment-resistant VLU
Milic et al. 2009 (48)	VLU	CBS	BMI>35	Increase risk of non-healing VLU
Yang et al. 2021 (49)	NIVL& SVR	EVLA	BMI>30	Increase risk of refractory ulcer

BMI (kg.m²), body mass index; SVR, superficial venous reflux; PVs, Perforator veins; PP, postoperative; IGSV, incompetent great saphenous vein; ISSV, incompetent small saphenous vein; IPVs, incompetent perforating veins ETA, endogenous thermal ablation; USGFS, ultrasound-guided foam sclerotherapy; MOCA, mechanochemical ablation; EVLA, endogenous laser ablation; EVLAS, endogenous laser ablation with stenting; AMPS, automated microfoam preparation system; VLU, venous leg ulcer; VV, varicose vein; CBS, compression bandaging system; NIVL, non-thrombotic iliac venous lesion; SVR, superficial venous reflux, CIVIQ, chronic venous insufficiency quality of life questionnaire; *Without comorbidity

Bariatric surgery as a treatment modality in CVD

Weight loss, whether through lifestyle changes or bariatric surgery, has been shown to improve venous hemodynamics and reduce CVI-related symptoms. Individuals with weight reduction following bariatric surgery demonstrated significant improvement in CVI outcomes compared to those who did not. These benefits included a higher rate of ulcer resolution, a reduction in the occurrence of venous claudication, and an overall enhancement in quality of life (37). It has been demonstrated that bariatric surgery in obese patients leads to improved venous hemodynamics, including a reduction in the diameter of the saphenous and femoral veins and an increase in blood flow velocity. These changes collectively contribute to higher wall shear stress (50, 51). Therefore, this vascular remodeling following significant weight loss could enhance venous circulation, potentially reducing the risk of venous insufficiency and thrombosis after weight loss. In another study although no significant change was observed in the diameter or reflux characteristics of the saphenous veins post-surgery.

Discussion

Bariatric surgery improved the clinical severity of CVD, as measured by the CEAP classification (52). While bariatric surgery does not appear to directly modify saphenous vein anatomy, its role in reducing venous disease severity highlights the importance of weight management in CVD treatment. Moreover, it has been suggested that some weight-loss medications have beneficial effects in improving the venous disorders. Semaglutide, a glucagon like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonist has been shown the potential to reduce venous pressure effects (53). On the other hand, bariatric surgery may predispose patients to thrombotic complications, such as DVT. A longitudinal study tracking a cohort of bariatric surgery patients over an average period of 7 years

revealed an increased incidence of venous disease. This was attributed to the patients' reduced physical activity levels, and endothelial damage (54). There is an intriguing observation that combination of mechanical and chemical prophylaxis seems to offer a significant advantage in preventing silent DVT after bariatric surgery. Patients who received both mechanical and chemical prophylaxis exhibited no silent DVT compared to those received only the mechanical approach.

Conclusion

In morbidly obese patients (BMI>35 kg/m²) with severe CVD, bariatric surgery should be considered a first-line therapeutic intervention, addressing the underlying cause of venous hypertension. Significant weight loss prior to venous interventions may enhance procedural efficacy, reduce preoperative risk, and improve long-term outcomes. However, close postoperative monitoring for thromboembolic complications is crucial, as bariatric surgery itself may transiently increase thrombotic risk. Prospective studies comparing different bariatric techniques could clarify which procedures offer the greatest venous benefits. Furthermore, collaboration between vascular surgeons, bariatric specialists, and obesity experts can optimize treatment sequencing and risk mitigation. Future research may explore whether venous interventions, enhance outcomes in post-bariatric patients.

Future directions and research gaps

There is no universal consensus on whether bariatric surgery or venous intervention should be prioritized in obese patients with CVD. To establish clear guidelines, large-scale RCTs comparing these treatment strategies are urgently needed. Such studies should evaluate long-term venous hemodynamic improvements, ulcer recurrence rates, and quality-of-life outcomes to guide evidence-based decision making. Additionally, emerging minimally invasive venous therapies, such as micro sclerotherapy and cyanoacrylate glue therapy, show promise as less invasive alternatives for obese patients who may not be immediate candidates for traditional venous surgery (55, 56). Another critical research gap lies in the comparative effectiveness of different bariatric surgery strategies including sleeve gastrectomy, Roux-en-Y gastric bypass, and gastric banding, in improving venous health.

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Long-term follow-up studies are essential to determine the sustained benefits of bariatric surgery on venous circulation, stent patency, and overall vascular remodeling.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

Disclosure Statement

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Authors' Contributions

All authors contributed to data analysis, drafting, and revising of the paper and agreed to be responsible for all the aspects of this work.

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